

ON SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF THE POPULATION TO THE NEWLY DEVELOPED STEPPE ZONES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE NUROTA OASIS)

Jumaev Jurabek Bobokul ugli

Independent researcher at the

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15472313>

Annotation. This article presents the author's views on the processes of social adaptation of the population relocated from the Nurota oasis to the newly developed lands.

Keywords: Uzbek SSR, Communist Party of Uzbekistan, Nurota oasis, Jizzakh, Syrdarya, Mirzachul, resettlement, population demography, migration, cotton, "Golodnostepstroy", steppe zone, mentality, state farm, settlement.

In the 50s-80s of the 20th century, much work was done in the Uzbek SSR to increase cotton fields and improve water management. This process could not but have an impact on the demographic and migration processes in the Jizzakh and Syrdarya regions. The ethno-psychological lifestyle of the displaced Nurota oasis population, their inner spiritual experiences, were not taken into account when developing new lands. The traditions of collectivism, tribalism, the continued existence of feelings of solidarity and solidarity inherent in the Islamic religion, formed among the oasis population, as well as the values of animal husbandry, shifting cultivation and semi-nomadic lifestyle in farming, were also ignored.

Nevertheless, not only the Nurota oasis, but also the displaced population from various regions of Uzbekistan and the Union republics, worked shoulder to shoulder in the desert and jointly carried out great creative work. The resettled population not only opened up new lands, but also made a worthy contribution to the development of agriculture, especially cotton growing, on state farms in the steppe [6:114-116]. As a result of the increase in the labor force, the productivity of the land increased.

In Mirzachul, cotton was sown on 181,000 hectares in 1962, and 12 centners of cotton were harvested from each hectare. A significant part of the harvested crop was supplied by farms affiliated with Golodnostepstroy. However, chronic disruptions in the supply and demand for everyday products made it difficult for the newly arrived population to adapt. In 1956–1969, 42,000 families were resettled in Mirzachul for permanent residence, and in 1969, 25,000 of them settled there. 17 thousand families, that is, 40.5% of all immigrants, were forced to return to their original places of residence [7:199].

Thus, until the 1970s, the resettlement of the displaced population in new lands was of a “temporary” nature.

After the 1970s, the resettlement of the population from the Nurota oasis to the desert zones was quite stable. In 1970–1973, the highest rate of resettlement (11,214 people) was observed from the Farish district of the oasis [8:87,88]. The population was resettled in such districts as Mirzachul, Pakhtakor and Arnasay, which were being redeveloped and where there was a high demand for labor. The specific traditions and customs of the population, religious beliefs, and the cultural and household conditions that were being created also had an impact on social adaptation.

The displaced population was forced to overcome problems associated with changes in their professional skills and economic and cultural qualifications in the new natural and social environment [1:19-21]. The improvement of living conditions created the basis for the formation of new habits in the life of the population. However, in many cases, the displaced population did not leave the ethnopsychology inherent in our mentality, the idea that “I will return to my homeland anyway” prevailed. As a result of the active development of the steppe, the population growth rate in 1959–1970 was -155.7% in the Jizzakh region, and -139.4% in the Syrdarya region. In 1970–1977, the growth reached 124.3% in Jizzakh region and 124.2% in Syrdarya region. The resettlement policy had a positive impact on population demographics [3:129].

Construction work on newly developed lands was carried out in the social sphere - schools, kindergartens, nurseries, outpatient clinics, cultural centers, clubs, libraries, health centers, communications - telephone, television, post, radio; utilities - drinking water, heating systems, gasification, electricity; transport communications - highways, passenger transportation, freight transportation. According to the resolution of the Executive Committee of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan dated March 31, 1969 No. 5-164, the construction of housing, schools, kindergartens, communication centers, a department store, a bus station, a bank, a citizens' meeting house and cultural institutions in the Ilyich, Pakhtakor and Mirzachul districts of the Syrdarya region was envisaged [11:197,209]. Special attention was also paid to improving the provision of medical services to the population. The resolution of the Executive Committee of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan dated March 31, 1969 No. 5-164 stipulated the sending of 92 doctors with higher education and secondary specialized education to the Mirzachul region of the Syrdarya region in 1969 and 115 in 1970 [11:197,209]. Such new

decisions served to a certain extent to improve the living standards of the population.

In the 60s and 70s of the 20th century, the pace of development of the steppe increased, and new settlements were built. In 1967, Mirzachul district was established on the basis of state farms No. 17, 18 and 19 in the Syrdarya region. By 1970, more than 14 thousand people of different nationalities lived in the modern city. In 1970, Dostlik district was established on the basis of Mirzachul district, and in 1971, the "Aq Oltin" district [17]. If only 3 state farms were established when Mirzachul district was established, then 13 new state farms were built over the next seven years, and magnificent modern settlements arose in the heart of the steppe.

In the new districts, state farms such as "Party XXIV Congress", "Soviet Russia", "Uzbekistan", and 5th Horticultural and Viticultural were established. In 1972, the cultivated area in the Mirzachul district was 14 thousand, and by 1975 this figure had reached 30 thousand hectares. 212 thousand square meters of residential buildings and many cultural and household facilities were put into operation. The provision of cultural and household and trade services to the population improved every year.

In 1978, more than 9 thousand various production, housing and cultural and household service facilities were built and put into operation in the collective farms and state farms of Uzbekistan by order of the village soviets. The total area of more than 5 thousand houses reached half a million square meters. 5,000 families of rural workers acquired new and comfortable homes. 365 newly built schools accommodated 152 thousand students, 343 kindergartens accommodated 32 thousand children, 68 clubs with 27 thousand places and hospitals with 3800 beds began operating in new buildings, hundreds of kilometers of water supply networks were built, and roads were improved [13:18].

By the mid-1970s, more than 300 large enterprises providing household services, 674 household service complexes, and household service houses with 929 reception points were operating in the republic [12:6]. Dozens of ateliers, household service houses, workshops, and factories united on a cooperative basis were launched in rural areas. For this, more than 90 million soums were spent throughout the republic during 1976–1979 [15:49]. However, the construction of preschool educational institutions and the attraction of children from young families to kindergartens have not been satisfactorily implemented. Such shortcomings are explained not only by the capacity of kindergartens, but

also by the fact that they are not equipped with the necessary equipment, educational materials, kitchen equipment, and the sewage and heating systems of the institution building are not provided at the required level [4:22].

In 1974, 2,644 residential buildings, 84 bathhouses, 325 hospitals and medical centers, 925 field sheds, 64.2 kilometers of water supply networks were overhauled by inter-collective farm and municipal service combines in the republic, and a total of 3,476 thousand soums of village improvement work was carried out [14:24]. According to the newspaper "Jizzakh Haqiqati", the administration of "Dzhizakstepstroy" concluded a business agreement with the Semashko Research Institute of Balneology and Physiotherapy in Tashkent to protect the health of steppe dwellers and ensure the productive work of rural residents [18]. Until the 1980s, a medical examination commission consisting of doctor T. Tolkocheva, a doctor who served in the Uzbek SSR, and scientific workers U. Otamurodova, G. Akramkhodjaev, F. Bakaev, A. Nurmuhammedov, and A. Azimova examined the health of desert dwellers [18]. Scientists studied the climatic conditions and hydromineral resources of the reserve oblast and registered healing water sources in 24 recreation areas. The number of healing water treatment hospitals increased from 3 to 11 [18].

The government also paid attention to school and educational work in desert areas. In 1968, the number of students in the oblast's districts reached 167,832. 38,363 students studied in city schools (Guliston, Jizzakh, Yangiyer). Boarding schools were built only in the cities of Jizzakh and Yangiyer [10:198]. The schools were mainly of the 1950s style, and the introduction of new teaching methods and the quality of lessons were not up to the mark. However, the opening of the Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute in 1974 played a significant role in directing the population living in the steppe to science.

During this period, students of universities and technical schools, as well as senior students of rural schools, were mainly involved in the long-term cotton harvest in the steppe zones. The younger generation, who did not have sufficient conditions, was forced to pick cotton while sleeping in the existing state farms in the steppe zones, in barns, and in buildings adapted for accommodating tractors. From 1965, 7th grade students, and in the 1970s, 5th grade students were also involved in picking cotton. According to the Commission for the Control of Children's Health, 10% of boys and 68% of girls aged 12-17 in schools had impaired natural growth processes and functional deficiencies were observed in them [5:41].

In the mid-1970s, the development of the agricultural sector in Uzbekistan also did not give the expected results. The socio-economic life of the nomadic population was affected by the development of cotton cultivation and its harvesting. The schoolchildren of the steppe state farms were gradually formed a sense of responsibility for the cultivation and harvesting of cotton. The widespread involvement of schoolchildren in agricultural work, such as cocoon picking, primary processing of cotton, ginning and winnowing of cotton, and cotton picking, could not but affect their future development.

Although pediatrics developed in the republic in the 1980s, environmental degradation led to an increase in child mortality in cotton-growing regions. For example, in Syrdarya region, child mortality in 1985 was 33.1, but by 1986 this figure had reached 44.0. The increase in child mortality by district was as follows: in "Oqoltin" - from 37 to 42, in Gulistan - from 32 to 53, in "Komsomol" - from 32 to 58, in Khovos - from 22 to 51, in Boyovut - from 27 to 37, in "Voroshilov" - from 45 to 450 [5:54]. The situation was especially difficult in newly developed areas like Mirzachul. The Ministry of Higher Education, in its order No. 537 dated July 23, 1985, decided not to involve students in agricultural work for more than a month and not to involve young people who worked in construction teams in the summer in field work [9:87,133]. However, all of them remained on paper. Repeated statements in newspapers and other media in support of these decisions and orders, as well as repeated warnings to the public, did not produce the expected results [19].

At that time, more than 5 million tons of cotton were grown in Uzbekistan. For this, almost 30 thousand cotton-picking and winnowing machines, more than 100 thousand mechanizers, and almost 2 million pickers were mobilized from 1,200 collective and state farms [9:87,133]. While it was possible to grow other crops than cotton in our republic and get more profitable, the Center focused all its attention on cotton cultivation.

The rapid development of new lands has caused damage to many vital components of the republic. The ever-expanding cotton fields have begun to crowd out other plants one after another. The violation of scientifically based crop rotation has dried up the topsoil of the land, worsened its reclamation condition, and caused salinization [2:19]. As a result of the unprecedented development of the Fergana Valley, Mirzachul, and Karshi deserts, the waters of the Syrdarya and Amu Darya rivers have not been used rationally. All these problems have accumulated and caused the Aral Sea tragedy [16].

In conclusion, the development of new lands has led to serious negative consequences, including the construction of new settlements, employment, and the resolution of some demographic problems. In order to strengthen the monopoly of cotton in Uzbekistan, a number of desert regions were actively developed. After the 1970s, the development of the deserts of the Syrdarya, Jizzakh and Kashkadarya regions was especially active. During this period, a large number of people were resettled from the Nurot oasis to the territories of the Syrdarya and Jizzakh regions, who gradually became the local population of this country.

List of used literature and sources:

1. Абдунабиев Л. Мирзачўлни ўзлаштириш тарихидан.–Тошкент: Уздавнашр, 1959.
2. Бобожонова Х. Ўзбекистонда ижтимоий-иқтисодий муносабатлар (70–80 йиллар мисолида). – Тошкент: Шарқ, 1999. – 160 б.
3. Болтаев А. Мирзачўл – Жиззах: ўтмиши ва бугуни (1900-2000 йиллар). – Тошкент: Фан, 2007. – 226 б.
4. Максакова Л.Л. Миграция населения проблемы и регулирования.–Ташкент, 2001.
5. Тагаев М.А. XX асрнинг II ярми – XXI аср бошларида Ўзбекистонда болалар тиббиёти тарихи (1950-2020 йиллар). Монография – Тошкент: EFFECT-D, 2022. – 192 б.
6. Эгамбердиев Р., Раззоқов А. Ўзбекистонда қўриқ ерларни суғориш, ўзлаштириш ва мелиорация тарихи: Мирзачўл мисолида. – Тошкент: “Фан”, 1984.
7. Эгамбердиев А. Воспроизводство трудовых ресурсов сельской местности Узбекистана. – Ташкент, 1972.
8. Jizzakh Regional State Archive, 13-fund, 1-inventory, 80-case, lists 87, 88.
9. National archive of Uzbekistan, 2806-fund, 1-inventory, 67-case, lists 87,133.
10. Syrdarya Regional State Archive, 91-fund, 1-inventory, 528-case, list 198.
11. Syrdarya Regional State Archive, 91-fund, 1-inventory, 797-case, lists 197, 209.
12. “Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги” journal. – №. 11. – Tashkent, 1974.
13. “Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги” journal. – №. 11. – Tashkent, 1978.
14. “Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги” journal. – №. 1. – Tashkent, 1976.
15. “Ўзбекистон қишлоқ хўжалиги” journal. – №. 9. – Tashkent, 1980.
16. “Ўзбекистон коммунисти” journal. – №. 10. – Tashkent, 1989.
17. “Жиззах қақиқати” newspaper. January 29, 1976.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

18. “Жиззах ҳақиқати” newspaper. January 25, 1981.
19. “Комсомолская правда” newspaper. September 10, 11, 1985.

